

Dissemination & Data Management Plan

Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme
H2020-MSCA-ITN-2014
Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions

Project no.: 642877
Project acronym: InnoChain
Project title: Building Innovation in the Extended Digital Chain

Start date of the project: 01/09/2015
Duration of the project: 48 months

Workpackage: 6 - Dissemination
Task: 6.1
Revision Date of this Deliverable: 22/01/2016

Authors: Martin Tamke (CITA), Mathilde Marengo (IAAC)

Organisation name of lead beneficiary for this task: IAAC

Dissemination Level: Other

R Document, report
DEM Demonstrator, pilot, prototype
DEC Websites, patent filings, videos, etc.
OTHER

Table of Content

1 Introduction

- 1.1 Objective and structure
- 1.2 Dissemination approach
- 1.3 Target groups
- 1.4 General dissemination and data management protocol

2 Project Identity

- 2.1 Innochain Logo
- 2.2 EU Emblem
- 2.3 Templates for dissemination
- 2.4 General publication protocol (Project identity)

3 Dissemination tools

- 3.1 Public Dissemination
 - 3.1.1 Research exhibition
 - 3.1.2 Website
 - 3.1.3 Social Media and 3rd party web platforms
 - 3.1.4 Newsletters
 - 3.1.5 Outreach activities to local environments, external web portals & communities
- 3.2 Scientific Dissemination
 - 3.2.1 Publication in international conferences, workshops and journals
 - 3.2.2 Colloquia and Pre-Viva seminar
 - 3.2.3 Innochain workshops
 - 3.2.4 Innochain Conference
 - 3.2.5 Innochain network journal
 - 3.2.6 Further Scientific dissemination activities
 - 3.2.7 General scientific Publication Protocols
- 3.3 Industry and community dissemination
 - 3.3.1 Seminars
 - 3.3.2 Publication in industry related press
 - 3.3.3 Further industry related dissemination activities
 - 3.3.4 General industry related dissemination protocols

4 Appendix 1: Research exhibition plan

5 Appendix 2: Public Event Plan

6 Appendix 3: Publication Plan

1.1 Introduction

1.1 Objective and structure

Part of the objective of Work Package 6 is to define the tools and processes through which information about the project is communicated to building industry, the scientific community and the general public. This document is to specify the necessary plan, that will guide the project's dissemination strategy and actions.

The essential parts of the plan are: what will be disseminated, who is the intended audience, what is the dissemination method and associated tools, and finally, when each activity will take place.

The plan provides for each dissemination tool protocols, to implement the dissemination aims and goals, and measures to evaluate the success of the dissemination activities.

1.2 Dissemination approach

Dissemination aims to spread research results and to promote the research ideas. It aims simultaneously to invite third parties to comment, participate and collaborate.

The Innochain network produces on all levels results, which can be disseminated. They originate from:

- work and collaboration of the individual ESR
- hosting beneficiary
- industrial collaborators
- the level of the network itself.

The results of Innochain take on many forms, from speculative design probes, and demonstrators to processes and methods, originating from the projects and collaborations, to discussions and novel concepts emerging in workshops, seminars, colloquia and conferences.

The Innochain network aims to include and activate all these levels for dissemination and to provide them with the right tools to create a broad outreach to the target groups.

1.3 Target groups

The dissemination is structured around three key target groups:

- Public (including civil society and media)
- Scientific
- Industry (including customers)

The Innochain network has a strong international inter-sector profile. Activating all partners to disseminate in their local environments and communities allows to reach out to the many levels of industry and academia - from design oriented architectural offices, to engineering firms, computational design communities and fabricators to the general public in many European regions.

Strong visuals and narratives are an important part of dissemination to all key target groups. The creation of images and videos is implemented on all levels of dissemination activities.

1.4 General dissemination and data management protocol

All results of Innochain should be published. All publication should adhere to the IPR agreement and protocols.

The Grant Agreement §29 DISSEMINATION OF RESULTS — OPEN ACCESS — VISIBILITY OF EU FUNDING describes in detail this general obligation to disseminate scientific results and prescribes as well procedures to inform involved network beneficiaries and industry partners about the intent to disseminate 45 days before publication and the right of other beneficiaries to object within 30 days of receiving this notification.

In Innochain the information about upcoming dissemination activities takes place within the monthly management meetings and are documented in the meetings minutes. Possible objections are to be raised via email to the network administrator and the concerned beneficiary.

Innochain is taking part in the [Horizon 2020 Pilot on Open Research Data](#) and will give the same amount of attention in publishing the research results underlying datasets, as to the publication of the research results itself.

2 Project Identity

A common reference identity in all dissemination tasks allows for better visibility and recognition as well as branding of the project. Furthermore, as also required by §29.4 of the grant agreement, all publications and presentations by members of Innochain consortium - including all ESR - must acknowledge the EU financial support received.

All dissemination tools and activities refer to the name of the project, to the project's website URL and to the graphic elements described in this section.

2.1 Innochain Logo

2.2 EU Emblem

Rules for the use of the emblem and download links can be found here:
http://ec.europa.eu/dgs/communication/services/visual_identity/index_en.htm

2.3 Templates for dissemination

The network develops a coherent identity through the engagement of an external graphic designer for the core publications of the network. The internal communication platform of Innochain will distribute templates for:

- Innochain network journal
- exhibition catalogues [example](#)

- event announcements in web (flyer) and print format ([example](#))
- info flyers on the general Innochain network
- info booklets for events [example](#)
- way finding signs for events

The internal communication platform will as well hold templates made from best practice of dissemination activities, which emerge during the network's operation, such as videos.

2.4 General publication protocol (Project identity)

Unless it is impossible or the Innochain Supervisor board agrees any result and dissemination document or action must:

- Display the Innochain and EU emblem with appropriate prominence and balance to each other and eventually other displayed emblems
- Refer to the project's website URL www.Innochain.net
- Show the following text:
 "This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 642877"

3 Dissemination tools

The network focusses on innovation in practice. This means that innovation is not limited to technological innovation but also includes the innovative potential of implementing known tools and processes to create new products and solutions. This requires dissemination tools, which are able to transport results as well as process and context of the conducted research.

The project emphasises tools that allow for engagement of the addressed target groups. It develops tools, which have the potential to address all groups simultaneously, as website or social media, and more targeted dissemination tools for public, scientific and industry dissemination.

3.1 Public Dissemination

Public dissemination aims to expose the broader public to the research questions, methods and results. The aim is here to invite non-specialists into the research context and communicate the overall aims of the network, the interdisciplinary breadth and the unique synergy enabled through the programme.

Innochain plans to establish the following activities. Additional public dissemination activities are expected to emerge throughout the project period, as for instance a public display in a gallery setting of the results of the Summer school in Berlin in project month 16.

3.1.1 Research exhibition

The research exhibition presents the material research undertaken as part of the research investigations. Research can often be alienating in its complexity. The gallery setting invites the public to experience experimental results presented as physical building experiments. The network plans three research exhibitions with each their scalar focus (Speculative Design Probes, Material Prototypes and Demonstrators). The research exhibition happen in parallel to the main scientific-evaluative research events (the two colloquia and the final international conference) that also are open for public participation.

Exhibition	Lead Beneficiary	Project Month
First year Exhibition "Design Probes"	IOA	18
Second year Exhibition "Prototypes"	KTH	30
Final exhibition "Demonstrators"	CITA	45

3.1.2 Website

<http://www.innochain.net/> is the central point of information on the project, its participants, progress and project related events. the webpage invites to participate and promotes the ideas of the network.

The web based blog continually disseminates the research events (colloquia, workshop-seminars and the final international conference) and each ESR will have an own project page on to which development on his/her project is logged. It acts as a means of communicating the network programme and posting the research results.

3.1.2.1 Website content

The website provides complete information on the network in the following categories:

Start page with strong visual identity. A rotating banner provides news and entry to different areas of the webpage. A short text introduces mission and vision of the network. The partners are introduced with images and rollovers, which provide access to the partner section of the page. Further elements:

- Join our Newsletter tab on the webpage
- A link to the internal webpage of the consortium.
- Link to the social media pages
- infoboxes on news, upcoming events, social media (integrates the #Innochain and other hashtags of the innochain participants)

About - gives general overview, vision and mission, work packages

Partners - introduces the work packages and provides detailed information on the partners with images, contact info and links to the projects, they are involved in, as their individual webpages

Projects and ESR - Provide an overview and entry to the individual research projects, including information on the involved ESR and partners and the ESR log books. Images and videos can as well be embedded through flickr image carousels and vimeo video.

Events & Training - shows upcoming training events, colloquia, conferences - and provides link to reports, videos etc. of past events. An embedded google calendar provides an overview. The page invites external parties to partake and provides means to register and sign-up.

Dissemination - the website is the central repository for the Innochain related publications (scientific papers, reports, videos etc) and datasets. The dissemination section lists all publications and gives access to their content, via uploaded files (i.e. pdfs) or through referrals to external providers and servers.

News - latest news from the network and extended partnership, announcement of new entries, as reports, journals, videos on the page.

The goal for www.innochain.net is to have, after the initial setup of the website, four new or renewed entries on the webpage per month.

3.1.2.2 Management of the website

The website is administered by the Innochain network administrator. His/her role is to create posts on networks events and dissemination activities, maintain the Innochain calendar of events, monitor the frequency of posts and their compliance with the Innochain publication protocols. He/she triggers the creation of posts in case of too little activity.

The rights to edit and author web content on innochain.net can furthermore be given to any member of the network in order to have ESRs and partners provide info on their project and aggregate in general many entries and diverse voices on the webpage.

3.1.2.3 Website protocols

All published content on the webpage may not harm others intellectual rights and needs to have a [creative commons zero license](#) or the respective agreement of the author(s) to be published. All published content on the web page needs to provide the full name of the author(s) and institution(s) where developed, the industry partnerships, as well as the name of the Network.

3.1.3 Social Media and 3rd party web platforms

Social Media is an effective way to spread news and content into all target groups. Innochain uses the unique tag #innochain on all entries on social media.

A presence on a range of platform addresses not only reaches many different target groups, but allows Innochain members to publish through appropriate channels.

Innochain is present on the following platforms, which addresses different target groups and have different goals:

Platform	Aim	Goal
----------	-----	------

Twitter	fast information on results and events	100 tweets with #innochain a year
Instagram	Dissemination of the visual appealing and spectacular. The Innochain instagram account shifts weekly to another ESR following the ESR project numbers.	150 posts with #innochain a year
Facebook	to address the general public with popular content from Innochain.net	30 posts a year
Flickr	a repository for high quality and high-resolution images from the whole project period	100 images a year
Issuu	hold publicly available publications from the network, as the network journal	2 publications a year
Vimeo	repository for videos made by individual ESR and the network of projects and activities and main Innochain events (workshop seminar, colloquia, exhibitions)	5 videos a year
Pinterest	to hold and collect and share visual information from the individual researchers	-
Github	Code created within the network is shared through GitHub. This allows for internal collaboration and tracking of the development and communication to and involvement to partners external to the network in writing code.	-

3.1.3.1 Management of social media

The network administrator stipulates the use of social media and manages the access to the social media presence of Innochain. If necessary he/she hands out the password and user information for specific users of the platform to network members in order to raise the dissemination activities.

All members of the network are invited to share the info on the network through their own profiles. They will use in any Innochain related posts the tag #innochain

3.1.3.2 Social Media and popular web platforms protocols

The #innochain tag must be used in all publications on Social Media and popular web platforms.

3.1.4 Newsletters

Innochain will establish a newsletter which informs about the release of the network journal, upcoming events and news from within the Innochain partnership including ESR, beneficiaries and industry partners.

The mailing list will be organised through mailchimp. Each beneficiary will provide a list of mail contacts. Industry partners will be invited to contribute. A “Join our Newsletter tab” on the webpage provides interested persons a possibility to opt in.

The goal is to have a newsletter every 6 month.

3.1.4.1 Management of the newsletter

The network administrator will collect the news for the newsletter and prepare and execute the posting with the leaders

3.1.6 Extended catalogue

The extended catalogue is issued after the final exhibition and international conference of the network. It disseminates the results to a wider audience of interested public, architecture practitioners, students and researchers alike. It is a durable record in which network researchers (practice and academia), ESRs and invited researchers partaking are asked to contribute with critically reflecting texts.

The catalogue is issued electronically and on print and follows established formats, such as the [Digital Crafting research](#) extended catalogue by CITA.

	Main topic	Lead Beneficiary	Project Month
1	Extended Catalogue	CITA	45

3.1.6.1 Innochain extended catalogue management and protocols

CITA is responsible for the extended catalogue and will develop it in collaboration with the workpackage 6 lead, the network administrator and the further Innochain partnership.

3.1.5 Outreach activities to local environments, external web portals & communities

The Innochain network and its members will multiply the outreach through the dissemination of events, results and news on external platforms (as. www.cultureagora.info), the local environments (as the beneficiaries webpages and calendars) and related communities (as. www.grasshopper3d.com).

This public outreach activities will include:

- presenting research to school and A level students
- developing themed workshops with bachelor and masters students
- participating in public dissemination event such as The Festival of Research, DK, European Researchers Night (UK) and Lange Nacht der Wissenschaften (DE)

3.1.7.1 Outreach management and protocols

Beneficiaries organising outreach activities will inform the network administrator in due time, who will post these on the Innochain webpage and relevant other dissemination channels.

Information and invitation on all overall network events of Innochain will be send in due time in electronic form through the network administrator to the beneficiaries and industry partners. These will implement protocols on their end to publish these events on their web platforms. They will provide the network administrator with contact data to send the event information to.

The network administrator will establish with the help of the network a list of relevant external platforms notify these in due time about upcoming Innochain events and news.

All posts have to link to the original page or the home page of www.Innochain.net

3.2 Scientific Dissemination

Scientific dissemination aims to share and critically discuss research at the highest scientific level. The scientific dissemination is further divided into internal and external dissemination:

Internal dissemination - shares and evaluates research results runningly so as to support synergy and critically engage in each other's research questions, method and results. Internal events centre on the evaluative research events (colloquia and pre-viva seminar) as well as the hands-on workshops (as part of the workshop-seminars). The internal events have a network focus but are open to the public from which we expect participation from an audience of specialists and researchers from practice and academia as well as research students.

External dissemination aims to make research results part of the larger scientific arena. Its core focus lies with progressively publishing of results in key scientific conference and journals.

The scientific dissemination tools are in detail:

3.2.1 Publication in international conferences, workshops and journals

Research results will be progressively published in key international research conferences, such as:

ACADIA, Advances in Architectural Geometry, Design Modelling Symposium, RobArch, Fabricate, IASS, IABSE (international association for bridge and structural engineering) and eCAADe

and journals such as:

IJAC (International Journal of Architecture and Computation) or IJSS (International Journal of Shell and Spatial Structures)

The goal is to have three scientific publications per year per scientific work package in a conference, workshop or journal external to the network.

3.2.2 Colloquia and Pre-Viva seminar

The two colloquia act as evaluation events in which research progress is assessed and scientific quality assured. The colloquia and pre-viva seminars are open events and also act as scientific dissemination to a wider scientific audience.

	Colloquium	Lead Beneficiary	Project Month
1	First year Colloquium & Exhibition "Design Probes"	IOA	18
2	Second year Colloquium & Exhibition "Prototypes"	IAAC	30

3.2.2.1 Colloquia and Pre-Viva seminar protocols

The Colloquia and Pre-Viva seminar are organised by a dedicated beneficiary in collaboration with the network administrator. Together they are inviting the public through broadly spread announcements on the web, flyers etc. The organising beneficiary is responsible for the documentation on event with good quality photo and video. The events will be reported via articles in the Innochain network journal, photo galleries and video on the web platforms of Innochain.

The ESR are asked to prepare 1 - 2 minute long videos of project progress for every colloquium. These videos will be put online before, during or after the event.

3.2.2.2 Final ESR report

The final ESR reports document on a scientific level the individual research projects conducted by the Innochain Early Researchers. They provide profound insights into the project's underlying research questions, related state of the art, the chosen method, the process and results of the work.

The ESR reports are shared with the public through the Innochain webpage.

3.2.3 Innochain workshops

The workshops are open events inviting researches and PhD fellows from beyond the network to participate in the hands-on learning environment. As such they act as scientific dissemination events that enable outreach and the sharing of methods and tools.

	Workshop	Lead Beneficiary	Project Month
1	Workshop-seminar 1.1 Communication design	CITA	12
2	Workshop-seminar 1.2 Simulating design	ITKE	12
3	Workshop-seminar 1.3 Materialising design	BSA	12
4	Workshop-seminar 2.1 Communicating design	KTH	24
5	Workshop-seminar 2.2 Simulating design	IOA	24
6	Workshop-seminar 2.3 Materialising design	IAAC	24

3.2.3.1 Innochain workshop protocols

The workshops are organised by appointed beneficiaries. The workshops have a network focus but are open to the public of specialists and researchers from practice and academia as well as research students. The organising beneficiary will in collaboration with the network administrator invite to the workshops via the web, flyers, local platforms etc.

The organising beneficiary is responsible for the documentation on event with good quality photography and video and the publication of these on www.innochain.net and the other Innochain web platforms.

The 6 workshops will be documented in the Innochain network journal.

3.2.4 Innochain Conference

The network will conclude in a large scale international conference with peer reviewed paper presentations from the field.

Conference	Lead Beneficiary	Project Month
Concluding international conference	CITA	45

3.2.5 Innochain network journal

The Innochain network journal aims to disseminate results to a wider audience of researchers, architectural practitioners, students and the interested public alike.

The format of an electronic journal is well known to the network, as in the [IAAC bits](#) or the [Digital Crafting research](#) report by CITA.

The journal brings together research results with focus on the material research (design probes, prototypes and demonstrators). It is a durable record in which network researchers (practice and academia), ESRs and invited researchers partaking in the evaluative research events are asked to contribute with critically reflecting texts. It prepares simultaneously the basis of the reporting in the respective Deliverables of Innochain to the EU commission.

The network journal will be free of charge and be distributed electronically through issue.com. This will provide a widest possible outreach and public accessibility. It will as well have an issn number, so that it can be found and referenced through professional channels.

The network journal is published after meetings of the whole network (startup, workshop-seminars, exhibitions & colloquia) this results in an approximate 6-month rhythm of its publication.

The goal is to have an overall number of 5 network journals.

3.1.5.1 Innochain Network Journal management and protocols

A dedicated beneficiary is responsible for the network journal. The beneficiary will develop the issue in collaboration with the work package 6 lead and the network administrator and engage other ESR and partners, where needed. They organise a peer review internal to the network.

Issue	Main topic	Lead Beneficiary	Project Month
1	Project startup, seminar, partners, participants and projects	IAAC	8
2	Workshop-seminar 1 series (1.1,1.2,1.3)	ITKE	14
3	Summerschool + First year Colloquium & Exhibition "Design Probes" The journal includes peer reviewed articles from the colloquium.	IOA	19
4	Workshop-seminar 2 series (2.1,2.2,2.3)	KTH	26
5	Second year Colloquium & Exhibition "Prototypes" The journal includes peer reviewed articles from the colloquium.	IAAC	31

3.2.6 Further Scientific dissemination activities

The Innochain network encourages members and partners to pursue further dissemination activities, such as:

- Participation in workshops
- Participation in conferences
- Books/Monographs

- Chapters in books
- Participation in activities organised jointly with other H2020 project(s)

The goal is that Innochain members attend 5 workshop and/or conferences per year per scientific work package.

3.2.7 General scientific Publication Protocols

Following the Grant agreements §29.2, §29.3 & §30 and the guidelines for the [Horizon 2020 Open data Pilot](#) the authors of every Innochain related scientific publication are obliged to grant open access to their **publication and the underlying datasets** and deposit them onto the central dissemination repository on www.Innochain.net. This has to take place

1. on publication, if an electronic version is available for free via the publisher, or
2. within six months of publication in any other case.

The bibliographic metadata must be open access and identify the deposited publication. It must be in a standard format and must include all of the following:

- the terms "Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions";
- the name of the action **Innochain**, acronym and grant number **642877** ;
- the **publication date**, and length of embargo period if applicable, and
- a [persistent identifier](#) . In case this is not granted through the publisher, the Innochain authors will take action to establish this.

The published **datasets** must furthermore be free to access and provide information — via the repository — about tools and instruments at the disposal of the beneficiaries and necessary for validating the results (and — where possible — provide the tools and instruments themselves).

3.3 Industry and community dissemination

Industry dissemination aims to disseminate results to the wider industry context.

The industry dissemination strategy intends to connect the network with a further partnership of strategic collaborators. This includes the invitation of high profiled individuals from industry to the networks scientific evaluation and dissemination events, such as colloquia, Pre-Viva seminars and conference, in order to strengthen the link and feedback from industry.

The use of visual media, such as video and images of Innochain events and demonstrators, supports the dissemination of eventually complex research results to an industry audience with minimal time for attention.

3.3.1 Seminars

The seminars have a strong focus on implementation and commercialisation. Linked to the hands-on workshops, the seminars invite practitioners and researchers to contextualise methods through real world examples and experimental research. The seminars are open public events and we expect an audience of experts from practice and academia.

	Workshop	Lead Beneficiary	Project Month
1	Seminar 1.1 Communication design.	CITA	12
2	Seminar 1.2 Simulating design	ITKE	12
3	Seminar 1.3 Materialising design	BSA	12
4	Seminar 2.1 Communicating design	KTH	24
5	Seminar 2.2 Simulating design	IOA	24
6	Seminar 2.3 Materialising design	IAAC	24

3.3.1.1 Innochain seminar protocols

The organising beneficiary invites in collaboration with the network organiser through industry related channels to the event.

The organising beneficiary is responsible for the documentation on event with good quality photo and video and the publication of these over www.innochain.net and the other Innochain web platform. The seminars will be documented in the Innochain network journal.

3.3.2 Publication in industry related press

The focus on implementation is further supported by a strong interest in publishing in professional industry press, which are typically Non-scientific and non-peer reviewed publications (popularised publications). In architecture and engineering there is a strong focus on industry press as a means of knowledge sharing.

We aim to publish research findings in central industry based journals such as:

DETAIL (DE), VDI Nachrichten (DE), TEC21 (CH), Arkitekten (DK), Ingeniøren (DK), Arkitekten (SE), Betong (SE) and Architect's Journal (UK)

3.3.3 Further industry related dissemination activities

During the course of the Innochain network further activities with a focus appealing to industry will emerge, such as:

- The summerschool “Drivers of Innovation” organised and run by the Innochain industry partner HENN
- Videos (of i.e. events, demonstrators)
- Participation in Trade fairs
- Participation in industry oriented conferences (i.e. SmartGeometry)
- Press release
- Industry directed flyers and invitations for training and other Innochain events

3.3.4 General industry related dissemination protocols

Unless it is impossible or the Innochain Supervisor board agrees any industry related result and dissemination document or action must:

- Display the Innochain and EU emblem with appropriate prominence and balance to each other and eventually other displayed emblems

- Refer to the project's website URL www.Innochain.net
- show the following text:
"This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 642877"

4 Appendix 1: Research exhibition plan

Innochain has planned three public exhibitions.

Exhibition	Lead Beneficiary	Project Month
First year Exhibition "Design Probes"	IOA	18
Second year Exhibition "Prototypes"	KTH	30
Final exhibition "Demonstrators"	CITA	45

5 Appendix 2: Public Event Plan

This plan provides an overview of the planned activities with public participation.

5.1 Innochain Conference

The network will conclude in a large scale international conference with peer reviewed paper presentations from the field.

Conference	Lead Beneficiary	Project Month
Concluding international conference	CITA	45

5.2 Innochain Workshops

The workshops are hands-on and share particular methods and tools. They provide the linked seminars with a solid base of experience to foster critical reflection.

	Workshop	Lead Beneficiary	Project Month
1	Workshop-seminar 1.1 Communication design	CITA	12
2	Workshop-seminar 1.2 Simulating design	ITKE	12
3	Workshop-seminar 1.3 Materialising design	BSA	12
4	Workshop-seminar 2.1 Communicating design	KTH	24
5	Workshop-seminar 2.2 Simulating design	IOA	24
6	Workshop-seminar 2.3 Materialising design	IAAC	24

5.3 Innochain Seminars

The seminars have a strong focus on implementation and commercialisation. Linked to the hands-on workshops, the seminars invite practitioners and researchers to contextualise

methods through real world examples and experimental research. The seminars are open public events and we expect an audience of experts from practice and academia.

	Workshop	Lead Beneficiary	Project Month
1	Seminar 1.1 Communication design.	CITA	12
2	Seminar 1.2 Simulating design	ITKE	12
3	Seminar 1.3 Materialising design	BSA	12
4	Seminar 2.1 Communicating design	KTH	24
5	Seminar 2.2 Simulating design	IOA	24
6	Seminar 2.3 Materialising design	IAAC	24

5.4 Further public outreach activities to local environments

The Innochain network and its members will partake in public outreach activities, such as:

- presenting research to school and A level students
- developing themed workshops with bachelor and masters students
- participating in public dissemination event such as The Festival of Research, DK, European Researchers Night (UK) and Lange Nacht der Wissenschaften (DE)

6 Appendix 3: Publication Plan

This plan provides an overview over the planned publication activities toward public, scientific and industry related target groups.

6.1 Innochain Network Journal (Public Dissemination)

The Innochain network journal aims to disseminate results to a wider audience of interested public, architecture practitioners, students and researchers alike.

A dedicated beneficiary is responsible for the network journal. The beneficiary will develop the issue in collaboration with the workpackage 6 lead and the network administrator and engage other ESR and partners, where needed.

Issue	Main topic	Lead Beneficiary	Project Month
1	Project startup, seminar, partners, participants and projects	IAAC	8
2	Workshop-seminar 1	ITKE	14
3	Summerschool + First year Colloquium & Exhibition "Design Probes" The journal includes peer reviewed articles from the colloquium.	IOA	19
4	Workshop-seminar 2	KTH	26
5	Second year Colloquium & Exhibition "Prototypes" The journal includes peer reviewed articles from the colloquium.	IAAC	31

6.2 Extended catalogue (Public Dissemination)

The extended catalogue is issued after the final exhibition and international conference of the network. It disseminates the results to a wider audience of interested public, architecture practitioners, students and researchers alike. It is a durable record in which network researchers (practice and academia), ESRs and invited researchers partaking are asked to contribute with critically reflecting texts.

The catalogue is issued electronically and follows established formats, as the [Digital Crafting research](#) extended catalogue by CITA.

	Main topic	Lead Beneficiary	Project Month
1	Extended Catalogue	CITA	45

6.3 Publication in international conferences, workshops and journals (Scientific Publication)

Research results will be progressively published in key international research conferences, such as:

ACADIA, Advances in Architectural Geometry, Design Modelling Symposium, RobArch, Fabricate, IASS, IABSE (international association for bridge and structural engineering) and eCAADe

and journals such as:

IJAC (International Journal of Architecture and Computation) or IJSS (International Journal of Shell and Spatial Structures)

The goal is to have three scientific publications per year per scientific workpackage in a conference, workshop or journal external to the network.

6.4 Further Scientific dissemination activities (Scientific Publication)

The Innochain network encourages members and partners to pursue further publication activities, such as:

- Books/Monographs
- Chapters in books

6.5 Publication in industry related press (Industry Publication)

The focus on implementation is further supported by a strong interest in publishing in professional industry press, which are typically Non-scientific and non-peer reviewed publications (popularised publications). In architecture and engineering there is a strong focus on industry press as a means of knowledge sharing. We aim to publish research findings in central industry based journals such as:

DETAIL (DE), VDI Nachrichten (DE), TEC21 (CH), Arkitekten (DK), Ingeniøren (DK), Arkitekten (SE), Betong (SE) and Architect's Journal (UK)